

FOREIGN EXPERIENCES OF ORGANIZING AND DEVELOPING ACTIVITIES OF THE HOUSING AND COMMUNAL SECTOR

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In the process of integration into the world economy, the implementation of structural changes in sectors and industries by all countries, taking into account the existing opportunities and potential, and adapting best practices to local conditions, is considered as a proven method for ensuring development. The development of branches and industries that exist, but economic relations do not meet the requirements of the time, based on the experience of developed foreign countries, allows to speed up the period of development of the branches of our country's economy to a certain extent. Development of the housing and communal services sector, which is the object of the research work, based on the use of advanced foreign experiences, opens the door to wide conditions and opportunities in the development of the sector based on free market relations.

The development models of housing and communal services sector of various foreign countries and the system of its implementation have emerged based on the formation of the housing and communal services system in these countries and the functioning characteristics of the formed system. Of course, the adaptation of these systems to the national service market and the management of the development of the sector by the state also have an impact on the optimal formation of the system and the introduction of innovations into the sector.

In developed and developing countries, the role and importance of the sector in the country's life is reflected in the activities of housing movement organizations organized at the national and international levels. Such organizations include the International Union of Tenants, which unites national organizations of more than 40 countries, the International Partnership Alliance, which unites more than 50 national housing organizations, and other international organizations.

Relatively active formation of housing and communal services system and service quality management based on innovation was observed in Great Britain, Germany, Sweden, USA, Finland, Poland, Romania, Czech Republic, Latvia and Estonia. In these countries, during the formation and development of the industry, their direct connection to the processes with the status of consumers and their joint participation in the processes are ensured.

Resident participation in the process is a two-way exchange of information and ideas that ensures their participation in decision-making and management. Local groups and local movements also perform important socio-economic tasks based on a realistic assessment of local conditions.

The structural changes to be implemented in the housing and communal economy in Central and Eastern European countries were initially left out of the mainstream of reforms. This situation, on the one hand, is explained by the fact that the main force of the reforms is aimed at the creation of priority tasks in the liberalization of the economy, multi-unit property, labor

market and capital forms, on the other hand, it is explained by the fact that in some countries, changes in the field of housing and communal services began before the transition to market relations. The transition to market relations has created the need for a comprehensive review of policies in the field of housing and communal services in all countries. In these countries, structural changes in the housing and communal sector have become an integral part of the ongoing reforms. However, the ways of implementing these changes were determined depending on the country's financial capabilities and the state of economic reforms. At the same time, the following general features can be distinguished, which are similar for many countries in the transition economy:

- an increase in the share of the private sector in the sources of housing construction financing;
- privatization of the housing fund;
- maintaining the housing fund and implementing changes in the payment mechanism for housing and communal services;
- change of mechanisms in the system of providing and maintaining housing for the population.

In the process of reforming the housing and communal sector, all countries face difficulties and conflicts of an economic and spiritual-psychological nature. One of the main problems is the regular increase in housing and communal services tariffs for the population. At the initial stage of structural changes in the sector, in many countries, service tariffs were coordinated by the state, but the population's expenses in this direction increased higher than the general consumption index estimates and real incomes. In recent years, there has been a tendency to change this situation, that is, the rate of growth of tariffs has slowed down, and there is a tendency to increase in the dynamics of the real income of the population.

Nevertheless, the expenses for housing and communal services came to the second place after the food expenses of the family budget. For example, housing and communal expenses accounted for 1/3 of family expenses in Bulgaria, and 1/4 in Hungary and the Czech Republic. In order to alleviate this situation to a certain extent, state programs in the form of communal grants, which provide financial support, have been implemented.

In Western Europe and the United States, the model of joint ownership of residential buildings - apartments, in which a housing association is formed (similar to a private housing association), is widespread. For example, in the Czech Republic and Slovakia, condominium members may prohibit the owner from selling the apartment until the utility bills are paid, or the owner may be required to sell the apartment at an auction and pay off the debt with funds. The priority direction of creating condominiums is the co-ownership of new constructions, new buildings, single objects, mainly houses, as well as other real estate.

Today, foreign models of housing owners' management regulate the legal and economic aspects of the purchase, ownership and use of residential premises at a high level. In this, first of all, the interests of citizens are taken into account. For example, much of the US housing stock is owned by private sector entities, and multiple forms of ownership in a single residential building are almost non-existent. The existence of several forms of ownership in residential buildings is common to many of our housing estates, which creates a number of unique challenges in housing management.

One of the best practices of managing the housing and communal economy is the experience accumulated in the Federal Republic of Germany.

On the eve of the reunification of East and West Germany, housing cooperatives accounted for 20%, private housing for 40%, and public housing for 40%. Today, 80% are owners, 15% are commercial owners, and 5% are communal housing owners' associations. In addition, 80% of private owners own housing cooperatives and rental houses.

Today, there are three types of ownership of housing and communal enterprises in Germany:

1. Enterprises providing utility services that exist as open joint-stock companies managed by a supervisory board with the participation of representatives of the municipality.
2. Associations of housing owners (in LLC form).
3. Private houses of employees of private enterprises.

Homeowners' associations differ from private homeowners' associations in Uzbekistan, in that each member of the partnership has one vote, and in the event of termination of the partnership, it is mandatory to pay a membership fee that is returned after two years.

In Poland, the management of the housing fund operates on the basis of the property of companies, associations of housing consumers, cooperatives and public construction companies. In this country, the cooperative form of housing fund management appeared in the 70s of the last century, and the state leased land plots to cooperatives for 99 years. In this case, the citizens paid for 50% of the house with the participation of the cooperative, and the state gave loans in the amount of 50% of the house's value. The main feature of this model is that cooperatives have the right to build commercial real estate (cafes, shops, parking lots) and rent it.

In Finland, another country of the European Union, the management of a house or apartment is regulated by housing or apartment joint-stock companies, that is, the owner of the apartment owns shares in the company that gives him the right to own the house in which he lives, and the housing owners' association is responsible for the entire house. A new form of ownership in this country is an apartment with the right of occupancy. To obtain title, the tenant pays the first 15 percent of the apartment's value upon moving in, but pays a higher rent to the housing association. At the time of leaving the lease, the tenant will get back the amount of money added when moving into the apartment.

The policy of housing and communal services system of France, one of the developed countries of the world, aims to provide additional funds for the improvement and repair of housing and neighboring areas by housing owners in return for the low cost of housing and communal services. In France, there are syndicates with legal status for the management of the housing stock, which unite the residents of the housing stock. Since 1965, in France, the right of property owners, forms, methods of property management, as well as the status of co-ownership have been consolidated by a legal document.

Sweden is another developed country with unique features in the field of housing and communal services. The unique feature of this country in this field is that about 40% of the housing stock is rental housing, and more than half of this percentage consists of houses belonging to the city municipality. There are a large number of tenants' associations in the country, and the number of families included in one association can be from 20 to 20 thousand. Due to the close cooperation between these associations and the state, the privatization of single-family houses has so far been prohibited, and the associations are usually managed by 5-9 people elected at the general meeting of tenants.

One of the best practices in the field can be seen in Great Britain, where reforms in the housing and communal sector lasted for 15 years. Water and electricity supply in the country

has been transferred to private companies. After privatization in this sector, the prices of utility services decreased significantly, but later the tariffs increased. Today, gas and electricity bills are growing by 6-10% annually. Citizens can easily change their electricity supply companies and they have the right to do this practice only once in a week. One citizen has the right to use the services of several suppliers at the same time, for example, if one supplier provides electricity during the day, another may supply electricity at a lower price at night.

The state of formation and development of the housing and communal services system in the Russian Federation is similar to the process in most CIS countries.

In Russia, this system was formed on the basis of the mutual relations of enterprises operating on the basis of monopoly and market mechanism, and the activity of three types of subjects is observed in the system:

1. Enterprise of housing owners (partnership basis).
2. Managing enterprises (private enterprises).
3. Contractor maintenance and operation enterprises and utility enterprises (commercial structures involved by management enterprises).

In the Republic of Uzbekistan, joint management of the housing fund in multi-family houses, as well as ensuring its maintenance, preservation and repair is carried out by private housing owners' associations as a voluntary association.

According to the comparative analysis of world experience in the management and organization of housing and communal services, the following main features of these services, which differ from European consumers in the CIS countries, can be distinguished:

- The average level of legal and technical knowledge of consumers in the housing and communal sector in Europe is much higher;
- if problems arise with the European consumer regarding the services provided, these problems will be solved by consumer associations or other public structures supported by the city municipality, in most of the CIS countries, the consumer will have to solve the problems on his own;
- European consumers have the opportunity to actively participate in the process of preparation and approval of regulatory documents in the field of housing and communal services;
- European consumers, in contrast to CIS consumers, have a higher sense of responsibility for the housing stock they live in and greater attention to ecology;
- everyone pays only for what he uses, so in western countries, much attention is paid to saving energy resources. In most of the CIS countries, some citizens do not have billing devices, but there are cases of overpayment due to the total area.

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